

ON STUDENTS' LEARNING RESULTS IN SMP NEGERI 7 IN JAMBI CITY

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Abstract.

Students' learning results are determined by several factors, one of them is external factors, such family, teachers, friends, school and equipment. Moreover, parental involvement in the process of children education is a form of cooperation between teachers and parents in determining students success. To support the students' learning results, the utilization of ICT as a medium of learning can be used. This study aimed to determine the influence of parental involvement and ICT utilization of students' learning results. The analyzed aspects include the influence of parents involvement in supporting students' learning results, utilization of ICT in supporting students' learning results. This study used survey design with data collection instrument in the form of questionnaire. The population of the study was the students of class IX of SMP Negeri 7 (State Junior High School of 7) in Jambi City. Random sampling based on class with amount as many as 125 people was applied in this study. This was conducted by using multiple regression with hypothesis test at level of significance 0,05. The result of the study showed that; (1) there is a positive influence between parental involvement on students' learning results with regression equation $\hat{Y} = 29,868 + 0,775X_1$, (2) there is positive influence between ICT utilization to students' learning results with regression equation $\hat{Y} = 57.598 + 0,564X_2$, (3) there is a positive influence between parents involvement and ICT utilization simultaneously toward students' learning results with regression equation $\hat{Y} = 26,503 + 0,659X_1 + 0,226X_2$. Based on the findings of the study, I can conclude that parental involvement and the utilization of ICT have an influence on students' learning results. Parents should spend more time accompanying their children in the learning process and in the utilization of ICT to support the students' learning process, and the cooperation further with teachers needs to be optimized to support the students success.

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1. Introduction

Every student who follows the educational process, would expect to be able to master the various competencies gained in the educational process. Students' mastery of various competencies, or more familiarly known as learning results, both cognitive, affective and psychomotor, is what will be the capital for students to live and face the challenges of life in the future.

The reason for putting parents as one of the factors that affects students' learning results is because parents are the first and primary educator for children. However, other polemics is parents also become part of that is not prepared. The reason, they must seek their own information and knowledge about how to grow and support the education of their children in positive conditions. Further, if talking about education then the focus of the conversation just often fall to the students and teachers while parents are often neglected in education. In fact, parents have a very big role in children's education. Moreover, each student has an opportunity to obtain optimal results in learning. However, the optimal results is not only dependent on the

students themselves, but also on outside factors of students themselves. They are parental involvement and utilization of ICT by students.

Based on the preliminary results, the data at least revealed a glimpse of parental involvement in children's education, it is revealed that 82.9% of students stated that their parents are actively involved in their education. Based on preliminary data, it can be concluded that the parents of students in SMP Negeri 7 in Jambi City actively involved in children's education.

Nowadays, information and communication technology has begun to be introduced in schools. In the field of education, information and communication technology, it is generally used in learning activities in schools that is better known as ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) or in the Indonesian language known as Teknologi Informasi dan Komunikasi (TIK) through the use of a computer which is well supported by internet technology or not.

According to preliminary results, the data revealed a glimpse of the description of ICT utilization in children's educational process, 80% of students stated that they are active in the utilization of ICT in supporting their educational process. In short, I concluded that the utilization of ICT by students in SMP Negeri 7 Jambi City looks active in helping children's learning process, the condition of parental involvement and utilization of ICT in students of SMP Negeri 7 Jambi City was categorized as quite high level, while the students' learning results are still low and need to be improved.

2. Methods

This study was a survey which one form of research aimed to get data from a certain place that is natural, and the researcher did the data collection by circulating questionnaires, so that the design of this study was a quantitative research in the form of survey with correlational research analysis and multiple regression. The population involved 341 students of class IX of SMP Negeri 7 Jambi City on academic year 2016/2017 and the number of samples from 4 (four) classes selected randomly as 125 students. Furthermore, the research chart on the influence of parental involvement, and ICT Utilization toward students' learning results can be described as follows:

Figure 1. Research Chart

Note:

- X₁ : Parents Involvement
- X₂ : ICT Utilization
- Y : Students' Learning Results

ε (epsilon) : Other related variables

Data collection techniques used a causal survey method with correlation techniques. Empirical data to be collected was about parental involvement (X_1), ICT utilization (X_2), and students' learning results (Y), from the respondents consisted of students of SMP Negeri 7 Jambi City.

The procedure of data analysis in this study began with the sequence steps as follows; preliminary analysis phase by doing the analysis using descriptive statistics included normality test, homogeneity test, linearity test, simple and multiple regression.

3. Results and Discussions

A. Description of Quantitative Research Data Result

The results of descriptive statistic with the result instrument of students' learning results had empirical data, for example, the lowest value was 73, the highest value was 99, the average was 87,57 and the median was 87,00. The parental involvement instrument consisted of 38 questions having empirical data, for example, the lowest value was 122, the highest value was 182, the average was 155,60 and the median was 157. The ICT utilization instrument consisted of 22 questions having empirical data, for example, the lowest value was 66, the highest value was 110, the average was 94,28 and the median was 94. The result of the estimated error normality calculation where $L_t = 0.0792$. The normal requirement was $L_o < L_t$ thus the standard error of $Y - \hat{Y}_1$, $Y - \hat{Y}_2$ and $Y - \hat{Y}_3$ was derived from a normally distributed population.

Table 1. Summary Of Data Normality Test By Using The Liliefors Formula

No	Error	L_o	L_t ($\alpha = 0,05$; $n = 1255$)	Conclusion
1	$Y - \hat{Y}_1$	0,0690	0,0792	Normal
2	$Y - \hat{Y}_2$	0,0598	0,0792	Normal
Normal Terms:		$L_o < L_t$		

Homogeneity of data variance of parental involvement on students' learning results, ICT utilization on students' learning results, was tested by using Bartlett Test. Data requirements are called homogeneous if $\chi_{count} < \chi_{table}$. Thus the parental involvement data group and the ICT utilization of students' learning results were from a homogeneous population.

Table 2. Homogeneity Test of Regression of Students' Learning Results with Parental Involvement and ICT Utilization

No	Grouping	X_{count}	X_{table}		Conclusion
			($\alpha = 0,05$)	($\alpha = 0,01$)	

1	Y over X_1	22,3250	101,8795	112,3288	Homogeneous
2	Y over X_2	19,2334	106,3948	117,0565	Homogeneous
Homogeneous Terms:		$X_{count} < X_{table}$			

Hypothesis Testing

a. The Influence of Parental Involvement (X_1) on Students' Learning Results (Y)

From the results of linear regression analysis both manually with microsoft Excel and SPSS will be proven hypothesis of the research on the influence of parental involvement toward student learning results. Referring from table 3, it was known that the functional effect between X_1 and Y can be presented in the form of regression equation as follows; $\hat{Y} = 29,868 + 0,775 X_1$.

Based on table 3, it can be seen the positive effect between variables X_1 on the variable Y obtained $t_{count} = 13,621$ with $t_{table(0,05)} = 1,9803$ and $t_{table(0,01)} = 2,617$ and probability 0,000. The Criteria of testing the significance is if $t_{count} > t_{table}$. It meant that parental involvement affected the students' learning results.

While looking at the value of R square (determination coefficient value) between parental involvement on students' learning results was $R_{y1}^2 = 0,6013$. It meant that 60,13% of variance with students' learning results can be explained by parental involvement. The following table of regression test result of variable X_1 toward Y.

Table 1. Regression test result of variable x_1 toward y

Model		Coefficients ^a				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	29,868	4,248		7,031	,000
	Parents Involvement	,371	,027	,775	13,621	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Results

Thus, it can be concluded the hypothesis of the study that stated there was a positive influence between parental involvement on students' learning results can be accepted. It meant the higher the parents involvement, the higher the level of students' learning results. Thus, the hypothesis was received.

b. Influence between ICT Utilization and Students Learning Results

From the results of linear regression analysis both manually with microsoft Excel and SPSS was proven by hypothesis of the study on the influence of ICT utilization toward students' learning results. The test results were summarized as in table 4.

Tabel 2 Regression Test Result Of Variable X_2 toward Y

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	57,598	3,974		14,495	,000
	ICT Utilization	,318	,042	,564	7,584	,000
a. Dependent Variable: Learning Results						

Referring from the table above, it was known that the functional effect between X_2 and Y can be presented in the form of regression equation was $\hat{Y} = 57,598 + 0,564 X_2$. Based on the table above, it can be seen the positive effect between variables X_2 on the variable Y obtained $t_{count} = 7,584$ with $t_{table(0,05)} = 1,9803$ and $t_{table(0,01)} = 2,617$ and probability 0,000. The Criteria of testing the significance was if $t_{count} > t_{table}$. It meant that ICT utilization affected the students' learning results.

While looking at the value of R square (determination coefficient value) between ICT utilization on students' learning results was $R_{y1}^2 = 0,319$. It meant that 31,90% of variance with students' learning results can be explained by ICT utilization.

Thus, it can be concluded the hypothesis of the study that stated there was a positive influence between ICT utilization on students' learning results and can be accepted. It meant the higher the ICT utilization, the higher the level of students' learning results. Thus, the hypothesis was received.

c. The Influence between Parents Involvement (X_1) and ICT Utilization (X_2) simultaneously toward Students' Learning Results (Y)

From the results of linear regression analysis both manually with microsoft Excel and SPSS was proven hypothesis of the research on the influence of parents involvement and ICT utilization simultaneously toward students' learning results. The test results were summarized as in table 5.

Table 3. Regression Test Result of Variabel X_1 and X_2 toward Y

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	26,503	4,168		6,359	,000
	Pemanfaatan ICT	,127	,036	,226	3,564	,001
	Keterlibatan Ortu	,315	,030	,659	10,403	,000
a. Dependent Variable: Learning Results						

Referring from the table above, it was known that the functional effect between X_1 and X_2 simultaneously toward Y can be presented in the form of regression equation was $\hat{Y} = 26,503 + 0,659X_1 + 0,226X_2$.

Based on the table above, it can be seen the positive effect between variables X_1 on the variable Y obtained $t_{count} = 10,403$ with $t_{table(0,05)} = 1,9796$ and $t_{table(0,01)} = 2,6167$ and the positive affect between variables X_2 on the variable Y obtained $t_{count} = 3,564$ with $t_{table(0,05)} = 1,9796$ and $t_{table(0,01)} = 2,6167$ and probability 0,000. The Criteria of testing the significance was if $t_{count} > t_{table}$. It meant that parental involvement and ICT utilization simultaneously affected the students' learning results.

To test the hypothesis that there is a positive influence between parents involvement (X_1) and ICT utilization (X_2) simultaneously toward students' learning results (Y), it is necessary to test the significance of multiple regression equation by using F test. The hypothesis requirement is accepted if $F_{count} > F_{table}$.

Based on the calculation of significance test obtained value $F_{count} = 107,947$ while $F_{table} (\alpha = 0,05) = 3,07$ dan $F_{table} (\alpha = 0,01) = 4,78$ and probability 0,000. It meant that the influence between parental involvement variables (X_1) and ICT utilization (X_2) simultaneously toward students' learning results (Y) was significant. That is, parental involvement and ICT utilization variables simultaneously can predict students' learning results. Multiple regression calculation of parental involvement and ICT utilization variables simultaneously on students' learning results can be seen in Table 6.

Table 4. Regression Test Result of Variabel X_1 and X_2 toward Y

ANOVA ^b						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2512,739	2	1256,370	107,947	,000 ^a
	Residual	1419,933	122	11,639		
	Total	3932,672	124			
a. Predictors: (Constant), Parents Involvement, ICT Utilization						
b. Dependent Variable: Learning Results						

Thus, it can be concluded that the hypothesis of the study stated that there was a positive influence between parental involvement and ICT utilization simultaneously toward the students' learning results was acceptable. Thus, the higher parental involvement and ICT utilization simultaneously, the higher the students' learning results. Thus, the hypothesis was received.

Table 5 Summary Result of Variable X_1 and X_2 toward Y

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	,799 ^a	,639	,633	3,412	,639	107,947	2	122	,000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Parents Involvement, ICT Utilization

Meanwhile, from Table 7 above, it was known that the value of R square (determination coefficient value) between the parental involvement and ICT utilization simultaneously toward students' learning results was $R_{y1}^2 = 0,639$. It meant that 63.90% of variance with students' learning results can be explained by parental involvement and ICT utilization simultaneously.

4. Discussions

1. The Influence between Parental Involvement (X_1) on Students' Learning Results

The result of hypothesis test showed that there was a functional effect between parental involvement on students' learning results with regression equation $\hat{Y} = 29,868 + 0,775X_1$ with the value of $F_{count} = 185,328 > F_{table} (\alpha = 0,05) = 3,918$ and $F_{table} (\alpha = 0,01) = 6,846$ which meant that the regression significance was very significant. The functional effect was linear as proved by linearity test with the value of $F_{count} = 1,497 < F_{table} (\alpha = 0,05) = 1,534$ and $F_{table} (\alpha = 0,01) = 1,832$ which meant non significant or the regression was linear. The value of correlation coefficient was 0,7754 and the determination coefficient between parental involvement on students' learning results was $R_{y1}^2 = 0,6013$. It meant that 60.13% of students' learning results were the result of parental involvement, while 39.87% was contributed by other variables that have influenced on the improvement of students' learning results.

The findings obtained in this study indicated that parental involvement in education can be realized in various forms of activities performed by parents either at home or at school, so that it will provide benefits for parents, children and schools. Parental involvement is a process to help parents using all their abilities to their own benefit, their children and the programs that run by their children. Parental involvement is the behavior of parents who are able to accompany, develop, influence, change, motivate, spur, and nurture their children, in an effort to develop all the self potential to a better direction for the present and the future. So, it creates the spirit of learning to realize the achievement in learning as well as on other activities optimally.

This is reinforced by the theory from Mansur (2005) that parental involvement in education is required at every level of education, where children begin the character building through the development of moral, religious, social, and emotional attitudes. The development of all these values can only be achieved maximally by the continuity of education at home and at school. Relevant research result conducted by Ristiani [2015] proves that there is a significant influence of parental involvement on students achievement, amounted to R is 0,616 with the determination coefficient (R^2) is 0,379.

Based on the above description, it can be concluded that the higher the parents involvement, the higher the students' learning results. Thus, the findings of facts and data in the analysis of this study further support the previous findings about the positive influence between parents involvement on students' learning results.

2. The Influence between ICT Utilization (X_2) on Students' Learning Results

The result of hypothesis test showed that there was a functional effect between ICT utilization on students' learning results with regression equation $\hat{Y} = 57,598 + 0,564X_2$ with the value of $F_{count} = 57,523 > F_{table} (\alpha = 0,05) = 3,918$ and $F_{table} (\alpha = 0,01) = 6,856$ which meant that the regression significance was very

significant. The functional effect was linear as proved by linearity test with the value of $F_{\text{count}} = -1,145 < F_{\text{table}} (\alpha = 0,05) = 1,532$ and $F_{\text{table}} (\alpha = 0,01) = 1,828$ which meant non significant or the regression was linear. The value of correlation coefficient is 0,5644 and the determination coefficient between ICT utilization on students' learning results was $R_{y^2} = 0,3186$. It meant that 31,86% of students' learning results was the result of ICT utilization, while 81,92% was contributed by other variables that have influenced on the improvement of students' learning results.

The findings obtained in this study indicated that the ICT utilization was a student attitude in using and utilizing ICT to support and facilitate the learning process in obtaining the required information. This is reinforced by the theory from Rosenberg [cited in Surya, 2011] with the developing of the use and the utilization of IT, impacting the shift in the learning process; 1) from training to appearance, 2) from classroom to anywhere and anytime, 3) from paper to 'online' or channel, 4) physical facility to network facility, and 5) from cycletime to realtime. Relevant research result conducted by Bachrintania [2012] proves that there is a positive and significant influenced of ICT utilization on students' learning motivation with R value is 0,522 and $p = 0,001$ ($p < 0,05$).

It means that the higher the ICT utilization, the higher the students' learning results, and vice versa, the lower the ICT utilization, the lower the students' learning results. By finding the facts and data in the analysis of this study further support the previous research about the positive influence between ICT utilization on students' learning results.

3. The Influence between Parental Involvement (X_1) and ICT Utilization (X_2) Simultaneously on Students' Learning Results

The result of hypothesis test shows that there is a functional effect between parents involvement and ICT utilization on students' learning results with regression equation $\hat{Y} = 26,503 + 0,659X_1 + 0,226X_2$ with the value of $F_{\text{count}} = 107,062 > F_{\text{table}} (\alpha = 0,05) = 3,07$ and $F_{\text{table}} (\alpha = 0,01) = 4,78$ which means that the regression significance is very significant. The value of multiple correlation coefficient between parents involvement and ICT utilizations simultaneously on students' learning results is 0,7993 and the determination coefficient is $R_{y.1.2^2} = 0,6388$. It means that 63,88% of students' learning results are the result of parents involvement and ICT utilizations simultaneously, while 36,12% are contributed by other variables that have influence on the improvement of students' learning results.

The findings obtained in this study indicates that if a student eager and earnest in learning, he will get the result of learning to a better direction. Meanwhile during the learning process and in utilizing ICT (Information and Communications Technology) which the students are always directed, accompanied, guided, and always monitor the children activities, it will be able to optimize the learning process that children do in developing self potential and it will also increase the value of students' learning results.

Thus, it can be seen if a student who has intense of parental involvement and good ICT utilization simultaneously will be able to increase the value of students' learning results.

5. Conclusion

Based on the research results and discussion about the influence of parental involvement and ICT utilization on students' learning results in SMP Negeri 7 in Jambi City, it can be concluded that; there was a significant positive influence between parental involvement on students' learning results in SMP Negeri 7 in Jambi City. Thus, the higher of the parents involvement resulted in increasing students' learning results in SMP Negeri 7 in Jambi City. 2) There was a significant positive influence between the ICT utilization students' learning results in SMP Negeri 7 in Jambi City. Thus, the higher of the ICT utilization resulted in increasing students' learning results in SMP Negeri 7 in Jambi City. 3) There was a significant positive influence between parental involvement and ICT utilization simultaneously on students' learning results in SMP Negeri 7 in Jambi City. Thus, the higher of the parental involvement and the ICT utilization simultaneously will result in the higher of the level of students' learning results in SMP Negeri 7 in Jambi City.

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